

Evaluation of elevation, slope, roughness, and vegetation type on the burn severity of the 2020 Calwood Fire in Boulder County, Colorado

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Abstract— The Calwood Fire burned in Boulder County, Colorado from October 17 through November 14 2020. The vegetation types in the area greatly influenced the spread and severity of the fire. The conifer forests burned most severely and the fire died when it ran out of fuel in the grasslands. The elevation of the land had very little effect over initial burn severity but the areas of lower elevation recovered faster than the areas of higher elevation. The areas of high slope burned less severely but recovered slower than areas of low slope. The areas of high roughness burned less severely in the initial fire than the areas of low roughness but did very little to affect the regrowth in the area.

aspect map (fig. 5B), using symbology after [5], and a roughness grid (fig. 5C) using a 3x3 window with the standard deviation of the slope [6].

I. INTRODUCTION

From October 17, 2020 to November 14, 2020 the Calwood Fire burned 40.9 km² in Boulder County, Colorado (Figure 1). The ignition source of the fire is unknown and strong winds at the time of the fire allowed it to spread rapidly across the landscape [1]. The fire began near the Cal-Wood Education center and spread east towards Boulder and U.S. Route 36 [2]. This study analyzes how topographical features like slope, roughness and elevation and the existing vegetation types in the area affect the severity of the initial burn and the regrowth rate.

II. DATA & METHODS

LandFire [3] provided the existing vegetation types of the affected area (Figure 2). The difference normalized burn ratio (dNBR) images are made with imagery from the Sentinel-2 satellites. NBRs [4] were created for 4 dates spanning the duration of the fire and the regrowth over the next two years. Each of the three NBRs from after the fire’s ignition were subtracted from a control NBR from, 28 September 2020, before the fire started (fig. 3, 4).

The elevation, slope and roughness figures were created from a 1m digital terrain model (DTM). A hillshade map (fig. 5A),

Figure 1. NIR images of the Calwood Fire burn area on 01 Oct 2020 (top) and 23 Nov 2020 (bottom). (Planet Imagery’s Super Dove satellites with 3m resolution)

Figure 2. LandFire 2020 existing vegetation with categories over 2% labelled.

Figure 3. Calculated burn area and recovery in km² from dNBR maps in Figure 4.

Figure 4. dNBRs created from Sentinel-2 images. All images were subtracted from an NBR of the area from 28 September, 2020.

Figure 5. USGS 3DEP DTM data: (A) hillshade, (B) combined aspect and slope, (C) roughness computed from standard deviation of slope in a 3x3 window.

The 1-meter DTM was masked to match the individual burn categories of the dNBRs and the data was compiled into histograms for corresponding to the elevation, slope, and roughness of the Calwood fire area (Figure 6)

III. RESULTS

Over half of the area is covered by two vegetation types: southern Rocky Mountain ponderosa pine, 49.9%, and the southern Rocky Mountain dry-mesic montane mixed conifer forest and woodland, 13.44% (Figure 2). The eastern border and southernmost point of the burn area are covered mainly in four types of grasslands and shrublands which cover 21.98% of the burn area (Figure 2).

Over the two-year regrowth period the reduction in the high severity burn area goes from 38.4 km² in 2020, to 16.5 km² in 2021, and 4.3 km² in 2022 (Figure 3). The apparent unburned area actually decreases from 41.4 km² in 2021 to 17.7 km² in 2022 (fig. 4) which also happens with the moderate high severity burn and the unburned area from 2021 to 2022 (fig. 3). The reduction in the healed land areas as the land recovers could be a result of the bin sizes used to process the data and create the dNBRs or a less productive spring and summer and therefore less vegetation than the reference NBR in September 2020.

The areas of high severity burn in 2020 occur most prevalently in the center and western side of the area. The areas of lower severity burn in 2020 occur around the southern and eastern sides of the burn area (fig. 3a). The regrowth occurs faster in areas where the burning was less severe with few areas of high severity burn remaining in the western half of the burn area by 2022.

Figure 6. Elevation, slope and aspect histograms for the post fire dNBRs for four categories describing the areas of high severity burn, moderate high severity burn, low severity burn, and unburned.

Figure 7. Elevation, slope and aspect histograms for the vegetation types found in the burn area in 2020 (from Landfire EVT).

The elevation of the area is higher in the west with values around 2600m and lower in the east with values closer to 1800m (fig. 5A). The Colorado flatirons lie in the areas of lower elevation

in the east (fig. 5A). The roughness identifies the location of prominent ridges and valleys throughout the burn area, the majority of which fall in the western half of the area (fig. 5C). The highest roughness values are around 25% and are located along the valleys between the mountains in the western section of the burn area and just north of where the fire originated (fig. 1 and 5C).

Figure 6 shows the geomorphometric characteristics of the burn and recovery areas immediately after the fire and the next two years. The elevation data show very little difference between the categories in 2020 when the fire burned; the areas of high severity burn averaging to 2183.2m and the unburned areas averaging to 2148.8m. In 2022 after almost two years of regrowth the average elevations get further from each other with the remaining areas of high severity burn averaging 2250.7 m, the areas of low severity burn averaging 1990.6m and unburned areas averaging 2025m. Aspect shows that the strong peaks with easterly aspect (Figure 6) corresponding with the preferred habitat of the Ponderosa Pines (Figure 7).

The slope data shows lower slopes in the more severely burned categories in 2020 (37.3% and 35.57%), 41.7% in areas of low severity burn, and 45.3% in the unburned areas. In 2022 the slope values of the high severity burn areas averaged to 44.5% and the unburned areas 39.78%. The roughness of the area affected the severity of the burning similarly to the slope in 2020: high severity 3.95% and unburned 6.3%. As the two years passed the range lessened and in 2022 the roughness values vary less; high severity burn averaging 4.1% and the unburned averaging 4.9%, so the rougher areas recovered.

III. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Vegetation type had the most effect on the burn severity of the Calwood Fire. The ponderosa pines and southern Rocky Mountain dry-mesic montane mixed conifer forest covered a large majority of the area and sustained the highest severity burns (fig. 2 and 4). The dry-mesic montane conifer forests grew on the uphill slopes and remained the most severely burned in 2022 (fig 2, 3, and 4). Both types of trees are most susceptible to burning in the spring and fall when their needles are the driest, with the Calwood Fire in October 2020.

The shrub and grasslands sustained less severe fire damage and regenerated more quickly than the forested area. The vegetation regrowth was observed in the dNBRs however these do not identify the type of vegetation that has returned to the highly burned areas and is not an indicator of the health of the ponderosa pine forests. The early regrowth could be grasses and; restoration efforts in the Calwood burn scar have already begun in an effort to replenish the ponderosa pines [1].

The analysis of the burn severity in the dNBRs when linked to the elevation, slope, and roughness maps allows consideration for the relationship between the factors. Elevation had little effect during the initial burn, and the lower elevation areas regrew faster.

The areas of lower elevation were able to recover more quickly than those of higher elevation, likely because the grasses that inhabit the lower elevation areas can regrow faster than the trees found at the higher elevations.

Initially areas of lower average slope were more severely burned than areas of higher average slope but regrowth occurred faster in areas of lower average elevation. The fire was likely able to spread easier through the forest in areas where the trees were on even ground and their flammable foliage was at the same height. Additionally, it is likely that there was less vegetation on the areas of higher slope even before the fire as the conditions are more competitive [7]. On slopes the fire would have had a harder time jumping from tree to tree. During regrowth it was likely easier for the vegetation to regrow in flatter areas of less stress where there was less erosion or chance of landslides [7].

The roughness data in 2020 from the initial fire shows that the areas of higher burn severity had much lower roughness. The areas with lower roughness were affected more greatly during the initial burn than the areas with larger roughness. When the data from 2022 is considered there is virtually no difference in the average roughness showing that it has little to no effect on the regrowth of vegetation.

V. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We thank Planet imagery for their satellite data. This project would not have been possible without discussions with MIDN 1/C Charles Dunn. All data was processed using MICRODEM [8].

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